

CEST imaging at 9.4 T using adjusted adiabatic spin-lock pulses for on- and off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ -dominated Z-spectrum acquisition

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Abstract

Purpose: The CEST experiment, with its correlation to rare proton species that are in exchange with the water pool, is very similar to the off-resonant water spin-lock experiment. In particular, low-power spin-lock Z-spectrum acquisition allows insight into $T_{1\rho}$ and exchange effects with decreased direct water saturation. Since the available spin-lock methods either require high B_1 power or are instable in the presence of strong B_1 and B_0 inhomogeneity present at ultra-high fields, the goal of this study was to find a robust adiabatic spin-lock pulse for on- and off-resonant application in the human brain at 9.4 T.

Methods: A series of Bloch simulations were employed to find optimal pulse shape parameters of an adjusted hyperbolic secant pulse applicable in the low power regime typically used for exchange-weighted spin-lock experiments. The optimized pulse was implemented and tested in phantom and in vivo experiments on a 9.4 T human scanner for on- and off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ - and Z-spectrum measurements.

Results: The simulation yielded a feasible pulse shape, which yielded robust images, less sensitivity to B_1 and B_0 inhomogeneity compared to previous spin-lock approaches and less direct water saturation, as well as a higher chemical exchange weighting compared to conventional CEST approaches.

Conclusion: By adapting a pulse shape for low-power spin-lock experiments, we were able to acquire robust on- and off-resonant adiabatic spin-lock prepared images in vivo at 9.4 T. This development leads directly to spin-lock Z-spectrum acquisition, beneficial for chemical-exchange-weighted MRI.

Keywords: CEST, CESL, spin-lock, $T_{1\rho}$

Introduction

Chemical exchange saturation transfer (CEST) MRI utilizes the transfer of magnetization of solutes to water via proton exchange. By saturating a relatively rare proton species that is in chemical exchange with the abundant water protons a relatively small effect can be amplified [1,2]. This effect allows enhanced detection of metabolites [3,4,5,6,7,8] and proteins in vivo [9,10,11]. The phenomenon can be understood by a mechanistic model: the magnetization of the solute proton is reduced by saturation, the saturated solute proton is transferred to the unsaturated water proton pool, and the magnetization of the water pool decreases until a new equilibrium is reached. Unfortunately, this mechanistic model is not able to clearly explain transient CEST effects, the interplay with direct water saturation, or semi-solid magnetization transfer (ssMT) contributions.

CEST can also be understood as a relaxation phenomenon [9,12] by considering the relaxation during radio-frequency irradiation, also known as the relaxation in the rotating frame $T_{1\rho}$, and $T_{2\rho}$ [13]. This theoretical insight not only allows us to understand the transient behavior elegantly as $T_{1\rho}$ -decay towards the new steady-state of $T_{1\rho}/T_1$, but also allows for incorporation of influences of CEST and MT contributions into the $T_{1\rho}$ - and thus the CEST-equations [14]. The comparison with $T_{1\rho}$ -measurements by the spin-lock technique (SL) also gives insight into how to reduce direct water saturation. In a typical CEST experiment, a long pulse is used to “saturate” a magnetization vector (Figure 1a). For a continuous wave (cw) experiment, this means that the CEST magnetization at the irradiation frequency rotates around the y-axis and decays (blue line, Figure 1a); at the same time, the nearby water magnetization vector follows the off-resonant rotations around \vec{B}_{eff} (red line, Figure 1a). SL pulses inherently suppress these oscillations and restore transverse magnetization after the locking period (Figure 1b). Instead of the on-resonant flip-angle behavior in a CEST experiment (Figure 1a), typically resulting in strong saturation and oscillation artifacts, SL allows insight into the on-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ -decay, which has itself a unique chemical-exchange weighting. At each irradiation frequency offset, the ideal SL experiment would only show $T_{1\rho}(\Delta\omega)$ -decay along the longitudinal axis of the rotating frame, while all components in the transverse plane of the rotating frame, namely $T_{2\rho}$ decay and any rotations, would be suppressed. An experiment with such ideal SL pulses would yield a $T_{1\rho}$ -dominated Z-spectrum with low influence from direct water saturation, and strong chemical exchange weighting in the magnetization of each saturation frequency offset. Thus, such a Z-spectrum would be beneficial for the acquisition and evaluation of CEST effects in vivo.

As shown by Jin et al. [15], chemical exchange-weighting in SL experiments greatly benefits from higher field strengths. Thus, in this work we aim to investigate Z-spectrum acquisition using SL pulses for in vivo applications at 9.4 T. While conventional on- and off-resonant SL experiments can be directly performed at a spectrometer, on a whole-body-system spin-lock approaches need to overcome artifacts due to B_0 and B_1 inhomogeneity. One approach to do so is using adiabatically-prepared SL pulses, which was shown to yield $R_{1\rho}$ -maps without oscillation imaging artifacts for on-resonant SL at 7 T [6]. However, these pulses cannot be used for off-resonant SL, since the amplitude mismatch between the adiabatic preparation pulse and the rectangular locking pulse leads to an erratic behavior of the magnetization (Figure 1c). In addition, even in the on-resonant case, at 9.4 T the same approach was not able to avoid oscillation artifacts due to the amplifier-limited maximum pulse amplitude. Matching the amplitude of the adiabatic tipping and the locking pulse improves the stability of the magnetization vector trajectory, since it overcomes this erratic behavior of the magnetization (Figure 1d). However, designing such a pulse is complex, regarding the limitation of the B_1 amplitude of the adiabatic pulse by the typically low power locking pulse.

The aim of this study was to design such an adjusted adiabatic SL pulse with matching amplitude, for on- and off-resonant use, to enable a $T_{1\rho}$ -dominated Z-spectrum acquisition. Design criteria were robustness against B_1 and B_0 inhomogeneity as well as a usability at low B_1 power deposition ($\sim 5 \mu\text{T}$). To achieve that, Bloch simulations were employed to find an optimized pulse shape which resulted the most similar magnetization behavior to an ideal SL pulse. The optimized SL pulse was then implemented and evaluated using phantom and in vivo MRI measurements at ultra-high-field (UHF).

Methods

Theoretical Description

An SL experiment uses a rectangular locking pulse, defined by an amplitude ω_1 and a frequency offset $\Delta\omega$, which is applied in between two tipping pulses (Figure 1 c,d). The first tipping pulse brings the magnetization vector to the effective frame, which is tilted by the angle $\theta = \text{atan}(\omega_1/\Delta\omega)$ with respect to the z-axis (see Figure 1b-d). For the on-resonant case, the flip angle of these pulses would be $\theta = 90^\circ$ and locking would occur along the transverse plane. The second tipping pulse, following the rectangular locking pulse, is used to tilt the magnetization back in z direction. When adiabatic pulses are used as tipping pulses, the on-resonant spin-lock pulse is prepared

by an adiabatic half passage pulse (AHP). The AHP can be described as a time-dependent vector $\vec{B}_{eff}(t)$

$$\vec{B}_{eff}(t) = \begin{pmatrix} B_x(t) \\ 0 \\ B_z(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} B_1(t) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{\gamma}(\Delta\omega_p(t)) \end{pmatrix} \quad [1]$$

where $B_1(t)$ is the amplitude and $\Delta\omega_p(t)$ is the frequency offset of the pulse, defined as the difference between the carrier frequency of the pulse $\omega_{RF}(t)$ and the Larmor frequency ω_0 ($\Delta\omega_p(t) = \omega_{RF}(t) - \omega_0$). A commonly used AHP pulse is the hyperbolic secant (HS) pulse described by the following formulas:

$$B_1(t) = B_{1,max} \cdot \text{sech}\left(\frac{\pi \cdot \Delta f}{\mu} \cdot (t - t_{adia})\right) \quad [2]$$

$$\Delta\omega_p(t) = \pi \cdot \Delta f \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{\pi \cdot \Delta f}{\mu} (t - t_{adia})\right) + \Delta\omega \quad [3]$$

Here, $B_{1,max}$ is the maximal amplitude, Δf is the bandwidth, t_{adia} the duration of the AHP pulse, μ is a dimensionless parameter controlling the *FWHM* of the HS function and $\Delta\omega$ is a constant frequency offset. The amplitude and frequency modulation of such a pulse shape for $B_{1,max} = 20 \mu\text{T}$, $\Delta f = 1200 \text{ Hz}$, $t_p = 8 \text{ ms}$, $\mu = 6$ and $\Delta\omega = 0 \text{ Hz}$ is shown in Figure 2a. The long plateau phase of the frequency modulation in combination with the late and steep increase of the amplitude modulation, leads to a fast rotation of \vec{B}_{eff} after approximately 5 ms and can cause violations of the adiabatic condition for low power pulses. Increasing the *FWHM* of the hyperbolic secant function, namely μ , results not only in a more gradual amplitude increase, but also in an amplitude offset at $t_0 = 0 \text{ ms}$ (dotted line, Figure 2a). This offset causes an erratic behavior of the magnetization, since the initial magnetization is not aligned with $\vec{B}_{eff}(t_0)$.

The adjusted HS pulse proposed here is depicted in Figure 2b. To overcome the amplitude offset, we introduced a windowed amplitude modulation (blue line, Figure 2b). For the frequency modulation, we chose an exponential function, to avoid the long plateau phase of the hyperbolic

tangent function (equation 3). This adjusted pulse shape is herein after referred to as HSExp. The windowing is defined by its length t_{window} , resulting in a time-dependent function $H(t)$:

$$H(t) = \begin{cases} t \leq t_{window}: 0.42 - 0.5 \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi \cdot t}{t_{window}}\right) + 0.08 \cdot \cos\left(\frac{2\pi \cdot t}{t_{window}}\right) \\ t > t_{window}: 1 \end{cases} \quad [4]$$

The complete description of the adjusted pulse shape then reads as:

$$B_1(t) = B_{1,max} \cdot \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{\pi \cdot \Delta f}{\mu} \cdot (t - t_p)\right) \cdot H(t) \quad [5]$$

$$\Delta\omega_p(t) = \pi \cdot \Delta f \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{t}{t_p} \cdot ef\right) - \pi \cdot \Delta f \cdot \exp(-ef) + \Delta\omega \quad [6]$$

The dimensionless parameter ef was introduced to control the steepness of the exponential curve. During the locking period with pulse duration TSL , the effective field $\vec{B}_{eff} = (B_1, 0, \Delta\omega/\gamma)$ is constant and the magnetization decays along the vector \vec{B}_{eff} , which is known as the $R_{1\rho}$ -decay ($R_{1\rho} = 1/T_{1\rho}$) described by

$$M_z(TSL) = (M_i - M_{ss}) \cdot \exp(-TSL \cdot R_{1\rho}) + M_{ss} \quad [7]$$

where M_i is the initial z-magnetization prior to the pulse, $R_{1\rho} = 1/T_{1\rho}$ is the tissue-dependent longitudinal relaxation rate in the rotating frame, and M_{ss} is the steady-state magnetization [9] given by:

$$M_{ss} = M_0 \cdot \frac{R_{1w} \cdot \cos(\theta)}{R_{1\rho}} \quad [8]$$

For on-resonant experiments, $M_{ss} = 0$. $R_{1\rho}$ depends on ω_1 , $\Delta\omega$, the relaxation rates, and an exchange term R'_{ex} and can be written as:

$$R_{1\rho} = R_{1w} \cdot \cos^2(\theta) + R_{2w} \cdot \sin^2(\theta) + R'_{ex} = R_{eff} + R'_{ex} \quad [9]$$

The quantity R'_{ex} is the exchange-dependent relaxation rate in the rotating frame and can contain exchange or ssMT related contributions [14]. The exchange dependent relaxation term R'_{ex} is defined by ω_1 , $\Delta\omega$, the concentration f_b , the exchange rate k_b , the chemical shift with respect to water $\delta\omega_b$, as well as the longitudinal R_{1b} and transversal relaxation rate R_{2b} of the solute pool b. Assuming the exchange rate to be much larger than relaxation rates of pool b ($k_b \gg R_{1b}, R_{2b}$), R_{1b} and R_{2b} can be neglected and R'_{ex} can be described by [12]:

$$R'_{ex}(\Delta\omega_b) = f_b k_b \frac{\delta\omega_b}{\omega_1^2 + \Delta\omega^2} \frac{\omega_1^2}{\Gamma^2/4 + \Delta\omega_b^2} + f_b k_b \sin^2\theta \frac{k_b}{\Gamma^2/4 + \Delta\omega_b^2} \quad [10]$$

With $\Delta\omega = \omega_{RF} - \omega_0$, $\Delta\omega_b = \omega_{RF} - (\delta\omega_b + \omega_0)$ and the linewidth Γ :

$$\Gamma = 2\sqrt{\omega_1^2 + k_b^2} \quad [11]$$

Equation 10 is valid for on- and off-resonant SL, but can be simplified in the on-resonant case to [13]:

$$R'_{ex}(\Delta\omega = 0) = f_b k_b \frac{\delta\omega_b^2}{\omega_1^2 + \delta\omega_b^2 + k_b^2} \quad [12]$$

According to equation 12 the exchange term is also present in the case of an FID ($\omega_1 = 0$), meaning that the observed R_2 , namely $R_{2,obs}$, is a mixture of the actual R_2 of the water pool and the R_{ex} of the exchanging pools, also known as the Swift-Connick relation [16].

$$R_{2,obs} = R_{2w} + f_b k_b \frac{\delta\omega_b^2}{\delta\omega_b^2 + k_b^2} \quad [13]$$

In the presence of a locking pulse this behavior turns from an FID into an on-resonant $R_{1\rho}$ decay:

$$R_{1\rho} = R_{2w} + f_b k_b \frac{\delta\omega_b^2}{\omega_1^2 + \delta\omega_b^2 + k_b^2} \quad [14]$$

Thus, equation 13 and 14 yield the correlation $R_{2,obs} \geq R_{1\rho} \geq R_{2w}$ for $\Delta\omega = 0$ Hz. The effect of the solute concentration f_b and exchange rate k_b on these terms is shown in Figure 3a and 3b, respectively. In the case of pure water, $R_{ex} = 0$. The observed R_1 relaxation rate is affected by an exchanging pool as well:

$$R_{1,obs} = \frac{R_{1w} + f_b R_{1b}}{1 + f_b} \quad [15]$$

Thus, $R_{1\rho}$ and the observed relaxation rates $R_{1,obs}$ and $R_{2,obs}$ are functions of the pure water relaxation R_{1w} and R_{2w} as well as of coupled pools. Pure R_{1w} and R_{2w} are unknown, as we can only measure $R_{1,obs}$ and $R_{2,obs}$. A direct quantification of R_{ex} by subtracting R_{eff} from the measured $R_{1\rho}$ is therefore not possible. To make a coarse estimation, we can use $R_{1,obs}$ and $R_{2,obs}$ instead of R_{1w} and R_{2w} as they are accessible, and equation 9 can be used to calculate a pure theoretical R_{eff} that we call $R_{eff,obs}$ here for comparison:

$$R_{eff,obs} = R_{1obs} \cdot \cos^2(\theta) + R_{2obs} \cdot \sin^2(\theta) \quad [16]$$

The decay of $R_{eff,obs}$ over different frequency offsets is shown in Figure 3c (black dotted line). In this simulation, $R_{eff,obs}$ is greater than $R_{1\rho}$ for $\Delta\omega_0 \leq 0.15$ ppm but smaller for $\Delta\omega_0 > 0.15$ ppm.

Equation 7 is only valid for a constant locking pulse but can be extended for an ideal adiabatic pulse by integration of the actual pulse shape using the step-wise approximation, which we refer to as $Z_{R1\rho}$, the $R_{1\rho}$ -dominated Z-spectrum:

$$Z_{R1\rho,n+1}(\Delta\omega, \omega_1) = (Z_{ref,n}(\Delta\omega, \omega_1) - M_{ss,n}(\Delta\omega, \omega_1)) \cdot \exp(-R_{1\rho,n}(\Delta\omega, \omega_1) \cdot \Delta t) + M_{ss,n}(\Delta\omega, \omega_1) \quad [17]$$

When using the eigenvalue approach as presented by Trott and Palmer [13] and Zaiss et al. [12], this equation describes an ideal adiabatic spin-lock, as only one eigenvalue (namely $R_{1\rho}$) is incorporated, with no oscillation eigenvalues and no $T_{2\rho}$. Thus, $Z_{R1\rho}$ forms a reference solution for an adiabatic SL pulse with perfect locking, yielding an $R_{1\rho}$ -dominated Z-spectrum. For a real

adiabatic SL pulse, all eigenvalues must be taken into account by integrating the full Bloch equations for shaped pulses.

Simulation

To find optimal pulse parameters for robust application in the presence of B_1 and B_0 inhomogeneity, a full Bloch simulation of the adiabatic pulses was performed sample-wise, using 200 samples per AHP pulse, as played out at the scanner. The pulse response was then calculated for 500 evenly distributed frequency offsets in the range of ± 3 ppm. This simulation was performed for 18 different combinations of B_0 and B_1 inhomogeneity based on the typical B_1 - and B_0 -maps in vivo at the used 9.4 T system. Six B_1 values ranging from 65% to 130% of nominal power (3.25 – 6.5 μT) and 3 ΔB_0 values of 0, 30, and 60 Hz were incorporated into the simulations. The resulting 18 Z-spectra were simulated for different parameter combinations of the proposed adjusted pulse shape (HSExp), namely $1 \leq \mu \leq 80$, $5 \text{ ms} \leq t_{\text{window}} \leq 3.5 \text{ ms}$, and $1000 \text{ Hz} \leq \Delta f \leq 9000 \text{ Hz}$, using the full Bloch equations yielding a stack Z_{full} , and using the ideal single-eigenvalue Bloch equations (Equation. 17) yielding a stack $Z_{R1\rho}$ as a reference. The cost function to be minimized was then the sum of squares of the difference (SSD) of $Z_{R1\rho}$ and the full Bloch solution Z_{full} :

$$\text{SSD} = \text{sum}((Z_{\text{full}} - Z_{R1\rho})^2) \quad [18]$$

Fixed parameters were $t_{\text{adia}} = 8 \text{ ms}$ and $B_1 = 5 \mu\text{T}$ as proposed by Schuenke et al. for the HS pulses [6]. The *ef* factor as described in equation 6 was set to 3.5, based on previous simulations.

MRI Measurements

MR imaging was performed on a 9.4 T whole-body system (Siemens Healthcare, Erlangen, Germany) under approval by the local ethics committee on five healthy volunteers who provided informed consent. Two different custom-built head coils were used for signal transmission/reception, either with 16 transmit / 31 receive channels [17] or 18 transmit / 32 receive channels [18].

The RF and gradient spoiled gradient-echo snapshot readout [19] of approximately 3 s was used with a base matrix of 144 with 80% FOV in the first phase-encoding direction and 18 slices. The flip angle was 6° , $\text{TE} = 2.13 \text{ ms}$, $\text{TR} = 4.2$, $\text{BW} = 560 \text{ Hz/px}$, resolution $1.5 \times 1.5 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$. Parallel

imaging acceleration factor 3 was applied in the phase encoding direction with GRAPPA reconstruction [20] performed offline. Prior to post-processing, all in vivo images were corrected for motion, using the AFNI's 3Dvolreg function [21].

T_{1ρ}-Decay Measurements

An on-and off-resonant T_{1ρ} measurement was acquired in a healthy volunteer. On-resonant the HSExp pulse was compared with the HS pulse presented in [6]. Since the typical B₁ distribution of 16/31 coil yields an effective B₁ amplitude of about 75% of the nominal value, the locking amplitude was set to 6.5 μT to achieve a mean value of 5 μT in the FOV. The maximum amplitude of the HS pulse was limited to 20 μT by amplifier restrictions, resulting in an effective value of approximately 15 μT.

The off-resonant measurement was acquired at $\Delta\omega = 1$ ppm and the HSExp pulse was compared with a single Gaussian pulse with amplitude matched to the continuous wave power equivalent (CWPE). For T_{1ρ} measurements, on-resonant SL prepared images were acquired with Gaussian and HSExp pulses at 19 different locking times from 0.5 to 50 ms, with denser sampling between 0.5 and 10 ms.

Z-Spectrum Measurements

Phantom measurements

In a phantom MRI measurement at room temperature, the HSExp pulse was compared to a clinical CEST protocol with Gaussian saturation pulses. The phantom consists of 7 cylindrical tubes filled with solutions of different glucose concentrations in a PBS buffer with a pH of 7.0. Glucose concentrations of the solutions in the tubes were 2 x 100 mM, 2 x 50 mM, 2 x 25 mM and 1 x pure PBS.

Using the HSExp pulse, the saturation phase consisted of two pulses with TSL = 100 ms with 75% duty cycle. Both rectangular locking pulses were surrounded by an AHP and an inverse AHP pulse. The Gaussian saturation scheme consisted of two 100 ms pulses with 75% duty cycle. Z-spectrum measurement consisted of 48 evenly distributed offsets between ± 3 ppm. For both pulses this Z-spectrum was acquired with different B₁ amplitudes, defined as the mean amplitude of a single pulse, of B₁=1,2,3,4,5 and 6 μT, resulting in 12 Z-spectra in total.

In vivo measurements

In vivo, Z-spectra were acquired with two different protocols. First, a single HSExp pulse using $B_{1,max} = 6.5 \mu\text{T}$ was compared to an amplitude-matched Gaussian pulse ($B_{1,cwpe} = 6.5 \mu\text{T}$) in the saturation block. The pulse duration t_p of the Gaussian pulse was matched to TSL of the HSExp pulse (50 ms). To reveal potential high frequency oscillation in the spectrum, 91 saturated images were acquired with dense frequency sampling at evenly distributed frequency offsets between ± 3 ppm. Recovery time between the measurements of subsequent offsets was 5 s.

In a second experiment, the hypothesis of less direct water saturation by the HSExp pulse was tested by comparing Z-spectra acquired with saturation from a train of HSExp SL pulses to spectra acquired with saturation using a train of rectangular pulses of the same amplitude. The saturation phase consisted of six rectangular saturation pulses with $t_p = 100$ ms and 50% duty cycle; identical parameters were chosen for the HSExp with $TSL = t_p$. A similar saturation scheme, but with a duration of 7.9 s was used by Rerich et al. [22] for a creatine weighted CEST contrast. Due to SAR limitations, this long saturation phase was not possible for our measurement. The Z-spectrum measurement consisted of 35 evenly distributed offsets between ± 4 ppm. Both of these protocols were repeated for B_1 amplitudes, $2 \mu\text{T}$, $2.5 \mu\text{T}$, and $3 \mu\text{T}$, providing glutamate or creatine weighted CEST imaging preparation [5].

Post-processing

All Z-spectrum data were corrected for B_0 inhomogeneity using the WASABI approach [23] and evaluated using MTR_{asym} .

$$MTR_{asym} = \left(\frac{M_{sat}(-\Delta\omega) - M_{sat}(\Delta\omega)}{M_0} \right) \quad [19]$$

Here, M_{sat} is the saturated image at a specific frequency and M_0 the unsaturated fully relaxed normalization scan (saturated at $\Delta\omega = -300$ ppm).

Results

Simulation

For the boundary conditions of $B_{1,adia} = B_{1,lock} = 5 \mu\text{T}$ and $t_{adia} = 8$ ms, the HSExp parameters resulting in the minimal $SSD = 0.573$ were $\mu = 45$, $t_{window} = 2.5$ ms and $\Delta f = 3000$ Hz. For all parameters, the SSD from the HSExp shape was notably lower than with a matching amplitude

HS pulse (Figure 2d,e). The deviation from the optimal $Z_{R_{1\rho}}$ curve for both pulses is shown in Figure 2c. Figure 4 shows the trajectory of the magnetization vector during the optimized HSExp pulse. The angle between the magnetization and \vec{B}_{eff} during the locking pulse remains small both on- and off-resonant, which suppresses oscillation artifacts. In the presence of B_0 and B_1 inhomogeneity, the magnetization vector still stays close to \vec{B}_{eff} .

On-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ measurements

The optimized HSExp pulse was implemented in a CEST sequence for 9.4 T and spin-lock prepared images of the brain were acquired in a healthy volunteer for different TSL times. Figure 5 shows the measured $T_{1\rho}$ -decay for a single voxel in gray matter (GM) and white matter (WM), that could be fitted with a mono-exponential curve, to determine $T_{1\rho}$ (equation 7). The resulting fit values from the HSExp pulse experiment, namely $T_{1\rho} = 45.4$ ms for the GM and $T_{1\rho} = 49.2$ ms for the WM voxel, were then used in a Bloch simulation, to verify the measured values. In both simulation and measurement, the HSExp pulse resulted in smaller oscillations than the HS pulse. Moreover, when increasing the B_1 power in the simulation, the oscillation almost disappeared for the HSExp pulse. This effect was not observed for the HS pulse.

The exponential fit was performed voxel-wise to generate an $R_{1\rho}$ -map. The on-resonant $R_{1\rho}$ -maps of the center slice using both pulses (HSExp and unmatched HS) are shown in Figure 6. The HS pulse results in visible artifacts in areas of low B_1 , while the HSExp pulse generates a flat image. The HSExp $R_{1\rho}$ -map is without oscillations, and only reflects the B_1 -dependency of $R_{1\rho}$ (equation 9). Thus, in the on-resonant case, the amplitude matched HSExp pulse with $B_{1,adia,max} \approx 5 \mu\text{T}$ performed more robustly than the HS pulse with $B_{1,adia,max} \approx 15 \mu\text{T}$. In ROIs drawn in WM and GM (Figure 6f), the measured $R_{1\rho}$ was 21.52 ± 0.64 Hz and 18.72 ± 0.76 Hz, respectively.

Off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ measurements

To test the HSExp pulse off-resonant, simple Gaussian saturation pulses were used for comparison, as the amplitude-matched HS pulse performs very poorly at low power (Figure 2d). The off-resonant $R_{1\rho}$ -map generated by the HSExp SL preparation showed no oscillation artifacts at 1 ppm (Figure 7e). ROI values for $R_{1\rho}$ using the HSExp pulse were 10.68 ± 0.48 Hz for GM and 11.36 ± 0.37 Hz for WM in the center slice.

The $R_{1\rho}$ values mapped using the Gaussian saturation pulse were 9.99 ± 0.29 Hz for GM and 10.02 ± 0.37 Hz for WM. However, several points had to be excluded to generate a proper fit

(Figure 7c), since the very short Gaussian pulses violate the adiabatic condition. The \vec{B}_{eff} of the Gaussian pulse is always moving, so the measured $T_{1\rho}$ value is averaged between the decay along the different \vec{B}_{eff} directions, which makes quantification more difficult. This result again demonstrates the ability of the HSExp pulse to avoid oscillation artifacts, even for very short locking times.

Z-Spectrum

Having shown good performance in on- and off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ decays, the HSExp pulse can now be applied for $T_{1\rho}$ -dominated Z-spectrum acquisition.

Comparison with Gaussian pulses in a phantom

Figure 8d,h,i show CEST contrast at 1.3 ppm generated by HSExp pulse. At a locking power ≥ 2 μ T, the HSExp saturation pulse showed a higher asymmetry than the Gaussian pulse (Figure 8m). The MTR_{asym} value increases with glucose concentration and saturation power for both pulses (Figure 8a,e,i). In the on-resonant case, the HSExp pulse generated images without visible oscillation artifacts, as long as the applied B_1 power is ≥ 3 μ T (Figure 8b,f,j). The off-resonant approach did not generate visible oscillation artifacts at any applied power (Figure 8c,g,k).

Comparison in vivo for a single pulse (SL regime, $t_{sat} \approx 50$ ms)

Z-spectra acquired with a single HSExp pulse showed a continuous curve along the entire frequency axis (Figure 9a), even in regions with a very low B_1 . Within the ± 1 ppm range the Gaussian pulse changes its behavior towards an on-resonant flip angle rotation of the water magnetization, leading to very strong direct water saturation, while the HSExp pulse only exhibits the on-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ -decay. This behavior can be seen in the Z-spectrum as well as in the asymmetry analysis. The MTR_{asym} images confirm the robustness of the HSExp pulse close to ω_0 (Figure 9f,g), where less oscillation artifacts are visible compared to the Gaussian pulse.

Comparison in vivo for a pulse train (CEST regime, $t_{sat} > 1$ s)

In a last experiment, a whole pulse train of six HSExp SL pulses or six rectangular pulses was used for saturation with $t_{sat} = 1.1$ s. Again, the SL-Z-spectra were more narrow compared to the conventional Z-spectra (Figure 10a). The frequency offset at 2 ppm was reported to correlate with creatine and protein amines [4,24]. The reduced direct water saturation led to stronger CEST effects at 2 ppm (Figure 10b). In GM in the center slice, the mean and standard error MTR_{asym} values at 2 ppm for the HSExp pulse were 3.98 ± 0.025 %, 3.23 ± 0.024 % and 2.14 ± 0.025 % for 3, 2.5 and 2 μ T, respectively. For the rectangular saturation pulses, the MTR_{asym} values were

$3.21 \pm 0.022 \%$, $2.62 \pm 0.023 \%$ and $1.56 \pm 0.018 \%$ for 3, 2.5 and 2 μT , respectively. In WM the mean MTR_{asym} values at 2 ppm in the center slice for the HSExp pulse were $2.26 \pm 0.024 \%$, $1.68 \pm 0.021 \%$ and $0.55 \pm 0.021 \%$ for 3, 2.5 and 2 μT , respectively. For the rectangular saturation pulses, the MTR_{asym} values in the center slice were $2.02 \pm 0.022 \%$, $1.35 \pm 0.019 \%$ and $0.19 \pm 0.02 \%$ for 3, 2.5 and 2 μT , respectively. In both tissues this difference was found significant based on a multi-comparison corrected ANOVA analysis. The stronger CEST effect was also visible in the MTR_{asym} image at 2 ppm (Figure 10c,d), especially in gray matter areas.

Discussion

In this work, we presented an adiabatically prepared constant-amplitude SL pulse, useable for on- and off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ -imaging and Z-spectroscopy at UHF. The acquired continuous Z-spectra in vivo showed very little artifact compared to commonly used techniques, such as unmatched HS SL pulses [6] in the on-resonant case or conventional Gaussian or rectangular CEST pulses in the off-resonant case. We want to point out that the applied amplitude ($B_1 \approx 5 \mu\text{T}$) is not low in terms of CEST imaging (often 0.5 μT to 4 μT [2]), but low compared to the typical SL amplitudes (5-40 μT [6,25]); thus, all experiments could be performed within the SAR and hardware limits at 9.4 T. As such a “low” power approach is especially beneficial for chemical exchange weighting of on- and off-resonant SL as stated in [26] and again herein, we provide a method for robust on- and off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ measurements as well as continuous Z-spectra acquisition with strong exchange weighting and intrinsically low direct water saturation which is also feasible for human brain scans at 9.4 T.

Many different approaches exist in the field of on- and off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ -imaging, with both adiabatic and non-adiabatic approaches. In an early work, Santyr et al. [27] used off-resonant SL pulses for breast cancer imaging at 1.5 T. Although they could show that adiabatic pulses are superior compared to classical SL pulses, their approach was based on a relatively long frequency modulation (30 ms) without amplitude modulation. A combination of on- and off-resonant adiabatic spin lock pulses was presented by Groehn et al. [25], who showed a positive $T_{1\rho}$ -contrast for cerebral ischemia in vivo with high-field MRI. However, very high B_1 amplitudes were used ($B_1 \geq 40 \mu\text{T}$), which can only be applied in animal experiments, since the SAR limit would be exceeded for humans. Going to UHF MRI, Jin et al. [15] presented off-resonant SL imaging at 9.4 T. With a conventional SL approach, they showed that the sensitivity and selectivity is higher in chemical exchange SL (CESL) than in a classical CEST experiment. Although they were using a low B_1 power, the conventional SL approach requires the homogeneous B_0 and B_1 fields achievable in

an animal scanner. Recently Schuenke et al. [6] presented an approach for on-resonant adiabatic SL imaging in humans at 7 T with a locking power of $B_{1,\text{lock}} = 5 \mu\text{T}$ and adiabatic pulse power of $B_{1,\text{adia}} \approx 20 \mu\text{T}$. This approach works well for on-resonant SL imaging and showed glucose hydroxyl exchange weighting in vivo [28,7] based on the change of R_{ex} in a tumor ROI of approximately 0.55 Hz after a glucose injection. However, the mismatch between the AHP and the rectangular locking pulse disables the possibility for off-resonant SL imaging. One approach to overcome this amplitude mismatch is to implement a ramp in the amplitude modulation, that takes $B_{1,\text{max}}$ from the AHP pulse to the value of the locking pulse, as presented in Groehn et al. [29]. Jin et al. [30] implemented this approach at UHF; however the B_1 amplitude in both studies was comparatively high (12 – 40 μT).

The presented approach is actually a generalization of the approach of Schuenke et al. By adjusting the adiabatic pulse shape, a HS SL pulse with matching amplitude could be designed to achieve both on- or off-resonant SL features. The presented work mainly focused on creating a pulse shape that is able to create images with as little artifact as possible. While the measured signals showed smooth $T_{1\rho}$ -decay, the $T_{1\rho}$ -time is a function of both $\Delta\omega$, and ω_1 and therefore also exhibits a modulation following the B_0 and B_1 inhomogeneity. However, intrinsic B_0 and B_1 weighting can be compensated for, similar to B_0 and B_1 correction in CEST imaging [23].

We want to point out that B_1 and B_0 compensation techniques are also available with conventional SL pulses. A good overview about correction techniques is given by Chen et al. [31]. However, this work includes only non-adiabatic approaches like rotary echo spin-lock [32,33], composite pulses [34], or phase-cycled composite spin-lock methods. Although, off-resonant correction methods were proposed, the presented approaches used high amplitude B_1 pulses, which would exceed the amplifier limit in our case. It might be possible to achieve similar performance with non-adiabatic approaches, which would be helpful in terms of SAR limitations, but this requires a comprehensive comparison and has to be studied in detail. The matched-adiabatic SL approach has the benefit that it is also very simple to implement as it is exactly the same amplitude and frequency pulse shape and only the frequency offset is changed. Thus, it is not necessary to adjust the flip angle to the frequency offset, as is required in conventional SL approaches.

As shown in the Theory section in equations 13 and 14, $R_{1\rho}$ cannot simply be separated in R_{eff} and R_{ex} , as pure R_{1w} and R_{2w} are unknown. In the following, the observed relaxation rates $R_{1,\text{obs}}$ and $R_{2,\text{obs}}$ and the $R_{\text{eff,obs}}$ value proposed in equation 16 are used for comparison.

During the on-resonant $R_{1\rho}$ measurement, the relative B_1 was $rB_{1,GM} = 98.24\%$ in the GM ROI and $rB_{1,WM} = 91.85\%$ in the WM ROI. The B_0 shift was $\Delta\omega_{GM} = 0.0767$ ppm in the GM and $\Delta\omega_{WM} = 0.0901$ ppm in the WM ROI. With $\theta = \text{atan}(\omega_1/\Delta\omega)$ this yields a mean $\theta_{GM} = 83.56^\circ$ and $\theta_{WM} = 81.92^\circ$. Assuming literature values for $R_{1,obs,GM} = 0.5$ Hz, $R_{2,obs,GM} = 28.57$ Hz, $R_{1,obs,WM} = 0.7$ Hz and $R_{2,obs,WM} = 33.81$ Hz at 9.4T [35] this leads to theoretical values of $R_{eff,obs,GM} = 28.22$ Hz and $R_{eff,obs,WM} = 33.68$ Hz. The measured values of $R_{1\rho}$ in this study with $R_{1\rho,GM} = 18.72 \pm 0.76$ Hz and $R_{1\rho,WM} = 21.52 \pm 0.64$ show therefore a discrepancy of approximately 10 Hz. Thus, $R_{eff,obs}$ incorporates exchange contributions of $R_{2,obs}$, and consequently $R_{1\rho}$ includes fewer R_{ex} contributions leading to slower relaxation. This result is in accordance with the simulation of $R_{eff,obs}$ (Figure 3c), as we expect $R_{1\rho} < R_{eff,obs}$ for $\Delta\omega = 0$ Hz. In comparison to previous work, the on-resonant $R_{1\rho}$ -map showed in [6], which was acquired at 7 T using an HS SL pulse, showed a discrepancy in the same range: the measured $R_{1\rho}$ in WM in their study was approximately 18 Hz, whereas $R_{eff,obs,WM}$, assuming $\theta_{WM} = 90^\circ$, would be approximately 27 Hz according to [35]. In MRI studies of human cartilage, the measured on-resonant $R_{1\rho}$ was also smaller than R_2 [36]. A detailed investigation in on-resonant $R_{1\rho}$ relaxation times in the human brain would be desirable in the future.

In the off-resonant case the measured $R_{1\rho}$ was 10.68 ± 0.48 Hz for GM and 11.36 ± 0.37 Hz for WM in the center slice. An offset of 1 ppm including B_1 and B_0 inhomogeneity results in a mean $\theta_{GM} = 32.25^\circ$ and $\theta_{WM} = 30.23^\circ$. This leads to $R_{eff,obs,GM} = 8.48$ Hz and $R_{eff,obs,WM} = 9.26$ Hz, again using literature values for GM and WM [35]. Interestingly, in the off-resonant case $R_{1\rho}$ has values above the theoretical $R_{eff,obs}$. Again, this result is in accordance with the simulation of $R_{eff,obs}$ (Figure 3c), as we would expect $R_{1\rho} > R_{eff,obs}$ at $\Delta\omega = 1$ ppm. It seems that off-resonant, R_{ex} contributions dominate $R_{1\rho}$ as the R_2 contribution is suppressed by the $\sin^2(\theta)$ term. Also the R_{ex} contribution increases if the irradiation frequency offset is closer to $\delta\omega_b$ (equation 10), usually located on the positive side of the $\Delta\omega$ -axis, which cannot be expressed by $R_{eff,obs}$.

Further quantitative investigation of the full $R_{1\rho}$ -spectrum is now enabled for in vivo applications and can be investigated in forthcoming studies. Comparing on- and off-resonant SL not only for different saturation powers, but also for different B_0 field strengths might yield deeper insights into these observations.

As shown in Figure 10, the MTR_{asym} values at 2 ppm showed a difference of around 20% between the HSExp and the rectangular pulse. As the applied B_1 was 2.5 μ T, the angle θ is small and we would therefore expect comparable MTR_{asym} values in the same range for both pulses, as $MTR_{Asym,CEST} = \cos(\theta) \cdot MTR_{Asym,SL}$ [12] [26]. For an amplitude of 2.5 μ T, this would only result in a

difference of approximately 1% at 2 ppm. Thus, the larger difference is unexpected, but can have several explanations. First, there could be some labeling during the frequency sweep of the adiabatic pulse affecting other CEST-active metabolites. Second, the asymmetry in vivo still has contributions from both sides of the spectrum. Although at the low applied power, the CEST effect from faster exchanging groups is enhanced, the slower exchanging NOE at negative frequencies still contributes and reduces the MTR_{asym} . Thus, it could be that CEST labels the NOEs more strongly than CESL. While these two arguments address the labeling, the most obvious difference is the reduced direct water saturation in the spectra. Thus, a third explanation might be that the magnetization vector after a rectangular pulse, which is only 100 ms long, is not aligned with the effective field and still has some residual oscillation component (see Figure 1a). This can lead to stronger direct saturation. These influences of SL pulses on spillover and labeling could explain the relatively large difference in MTR_{asym} . However, these effects must be further investigated for quantification of exchange mechanisms in the $R_{1\rho}$ -spectrum.

We do not claim the proposed HSExp pulse to be the optimal pulse shape for constant-amplitude adiabatic spin-lock applications. This study was rather a feasibility test of whether we can implement a stable, matching amplitude low-power adiabatic spin-lock pulse at UHF. By investigating a new mathematical function for the pulse shape with more degrees of freedom and using simulations for parameter optimization, we were able to find a reasonable shape for our applications. However, we think that the pulse design can still be improved. Potential considerations for finding optimal pulse parameters could be Shinnar-LeRoux-algorithms [37] or optimal control approaches [38,39] using the desired $T_{1\rho}$ -dominated Z-spectrum as part of the design criteria. The present study shows that this optimization can be run with a matched pulse and the boundary conditions of $B_1 = 5 \mu\text{T}$ and $t_{adia} = 8 \text{ ms}$. With future optimizations, both B_1 and t_{adia} can potentially be further decreased.

Finally, if the desired application requires off-resonant saturation at frequencies $|\Delta\omega| > 100 \text{ Hz}$ and B_1 power below $5 \mu\text{T}$, conventional shaped pulses perform very well and are simpler to implement and use.

Conclusion:

By adapting the pulse shape of the adiabatic half passage pulse, we were able to acquire robust on- and off-resonant spin-lock prepared $T_{1\rho}$ -weighted images. Both on-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ images as well as off-resonant CEST images showed only minor artifacts despite large field inhomogeneity

at 9.4 T. Furthermore, the chemical exchange weighting was higher with the proposed pulse compared to conventional CEST methods. The proposed pulse is a proof-of-principle that matched adiabatic pulses can be used for improved CEST preparation at B_1 powers as low as $3 \mu\text{T}$, and suggests that further optimization of spin-lock pulses for different field strengths and applications are possible.

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Figures

Figure 1: Amplitude ($\omega_1(t)$) and frequency ($\omega_{RF}(t) - \omega_0$) modulation and the corresponding trajectory of the Magnetization vector for a continuous wave CEST (a), conventional Spin-Lock (b), hyperbolic secant non-matching Spin-Lock (c) and a hyperbolic secant matching Spin-Lock (d) saturation scheme. Blue lines show the on-resonant trajectory, red lines the trajectory at 2 ppm. The tip of the magnetization vector at the end of the pulse is marked with a colored dot in the graph. In (a) the on-resonant saturation is just a rotation around the y' -axis. Applied off-resonant, the magnetization rotates around the effective field $B_{eff} = (B_1, 0, \Delta\omega/\gamma)$. The classical SL in (b) shows the ideal result at optimal conditions. The rotations are suppressed in both cases. However, B_0 and B_1 inhomogeneity can strongly disturb this behavior. (c): while the on-resonant case yields robust spin-lock (the B_{eff} direction stays stationary during the whole pulse) the off-resonant case shows strong oscillations similar to (a). In (d) the power of the locking pulse was matched to the power of the adiabatic tilting pulse. This pulse yields controlled magnetization both on- and off-resonant, as in the ideal SL (b), but is robust against B_0 and B_1 inhomogeneity.

Figure 2: Optimization of conventional HS and novel HSExp pulses with matching amplitude $B_1 = 5 \mu\text{T}$. (a) and (b) show the amplitude (blue lines) and frequency (red lines) modulation of the pulse for exemplary parameters. (c): Example of the simulated (solid lines) and the optimal Z-spectrum (dashed lines) for the HS pulse presented in [6] with $B_{1,adia} = 5 \mu\text{T}$ and the proposed HSExp pulse with $\mu=45$, $\Delta f = 3000 \text{ Hz}$ and $t_{window} = 2.5 \text{ ms}$. The HSExp pulse shows a lower oscillation and therefore a lower sum-of-squared-difference between the simulated and the optimal points. The sum-of-squared-difference can be used as a cost function and is plotted for each parameter setting for the HS pulse (d) and the HSExp pulse (e).

Figure 3: Simulations of influence of k_b , B_1 and $\Delta\omega$ on the observed relaxation rate for a CEST pool with parameters $f_b = 0.0027$, $k_b = 3500 \text{ Hz}$, $\delta\omega_b = 1.3 \text{ ppm}$, $R_{2b} = 30 \text{ Hz}$, $R_{1b} = 1 \text{ Hz}$ and a water pool with parameters $R_{1w} = 1 \text{ Hz}$, $R_{2w} = 25.6 \text{ Hz}$. (a) shows the influence of k_b with a constant $B_1 = 5 \mu\text{T}$. If $k_b = 0$, then $R_{\text{ex}} = 0$ and thus $R_{2w} = R_{2,\text{obs}} = R_{1\rho}$. If $k_b > 0$, then $R_{\text{ex}} > 0$ and thus $R_{2,\text{obs}} > R_{1\rho} > R_{2w}$. (b) shows the influence of B_1 with a constant $k_b = 3500 \text{ Hz}$. In that case, R_{ex} is always greater than 0. Therefore, when $B_1 = 0$ we have $R_{2,\text{obs}} = R_{1\rho} > R_{2w}$. When $B_1 > 0$ we have $R_{2,\text{obs}} > R_{1\rho} > R_{2w}$. $R_{2,\text{obs}}$ stays constant as its R_{ex} term is independent of B_1 (equation 13). (c) shows $R_{1\rho}$ as function of $\Delta\omega$ and its contributors R_{eff} and R_{ex} for a continuous wave irradiation of 200 ms. If $\Delta\omega = 0$ then $R_{2,\text{obs}} > R_{1\rho}$. $R_{\text{eff,obs}}$ (black dotted line) is a theoretical value for the observed R_{eff} (equation 16).

Figure 4: (a-c) show the trajectory of the magnetization vector during the HSEXP spin-lock pulse, with (a) showing the on-resonant case without field inhomogeneity, (b) showing the trajectory at 1 ppm without field inhomogeneity, and (c) showing the on-resonant SL pulse in the presence of B_0 inhomogeneity. The different phases of the SL pulse are shown in (d).

Figure 5: Performance of $T_{1\rho}$ measurement with the on-resonant SL pulses non-matched HS (a,b) and matched HSExp (c,d) in a single-voxel of gray matter (a,c) and white matter (b,d). The field inhomogeneities in the GM and WM voxel were 0.11 ppm/ 0.04 ppm for B_0 and 60.5%/ 67.4% for B_1 , respectively, and lead to the visible oscillations in the decay curves of the HS pulse (red markers in (a,b)). Oscillations are similar in magnitude when simulations include inhomogeneities (blue lines in a,b). In comparison, the HSExp pulse generates smaller oscillations in both experimental (red markers in c,d) and simulated data (blue lines in c,d), even though the applied tipping power of 6.5 μT was less than a third of the power applied by the HS pulse. The black lines show the simulated decay curves for the nominal $B_1 = 5 \mu\text{T}$. Here the oscillation almost disappears using the HSExp pulse, but not using the non-matched HS pulse.

Figure 6: Parameter maps from the mono-exponential fit of $T_{1\rho}$ -decay, namely $M(t_0)$ (a,e), and $R_{1\rho}$ (b,f) for the HS-prepared SL (a,b) and the HSExp pulse (e,f). Panels (c) and (g) show the $T_{1\rho}$ -weighted image at TSL = 30 ms. The HS prepared SL images (b,c) exhibit strong oscillation artifacts (red arrows) in regions of low B_1 (d). These artifacts are suppressed in the maps obtained by HSExp SL preparation (f,g). Neither pulse exhibits severe influence from B_0 inhomogeneity (h). A GM (red line) and WM (black line) ROI for data evaluation are shown in (f).

Figure 7: Off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ -maps from Gaussian (a,b) and HSEp SL preparation (d,e). The corresponding B_0 and B_1 maps are given in Figure 6 (d,h). All maps show smooth results and no oscillation artifacts. Since the off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ is a function of B_1 (equation 9), a correlation with the B_1 map is visible (a-d). Panels (c,f) show exponential fits (solid lines) of the measured off-resonant $T_{1\rho}$ -decay values (circles) for Gaussian (c) and the HSEp pulse preparation (f). The off-resonant Gaussian pulse shows adiabatic behavior as long as the pulse duration is long enough; with short pulses, this condition is violated and the Z-values oscillate (black circles in c). For that reason, the first 7 sample points have been excluded prior to fitting. In contrast, Z-values in (f) show almost no oscillation.

Figure 8: Glucose phantom measurement using HSExp pulses for different glucose concentrations as noted in (c). The 1st, 2nd and 3rd row show the results for 5, 3 and 1 μT saturation pulses, respectively. The first column (a,e,i) shows the MTR_{asym} in three different glucose concentrations (100, 50 and 25 mM). The 2nd column shows the on-resonant $T_{1\rho\text{w}}$ -images of the HSExp pulse (b,f,j); the 3rd row shows the $T_{1\rho\text{w}}$ -images of the HSExp pulse at 1.3 ppm (c,g,k). The 4th column shows the MTR_{asym} images at 1.3 ppm (d,h,l). Figure (n) shows the relative B_1 map and (o) the ΔB_0 map [ppm]. At 3 μT , the on-resonant image (f) shows artifacts in regions with low B_1 . At 1 μT , the adiabatic condition is heavily violated leading to severe artifacts

in the on-resonant image (j). The images at 1.3 ppm are free of oscillation artifacts for all B_1 amplitudes (c,g,k). The MTR_{asym} (1.3 ppm) as a function of B_1 is shown in (m) for both the Gaussian and the HSExp pulse. For $B_1 > 2 \mu\text{T}$ MTR_{asym} from the HSExp pulse is higher compared to the Gaussian pulse: at maximum labeling the HSExp pulse yields ~ 1.3 times the CEST effect obtained with Gaussian pulse. The error bars indicate the standard deviation in the ROI. The high MTR_{asym} values at approx. 0.13 ppm for the Gaussian pulse are due to oscillation imaging artifacts.

Figure 9: In vivo Z-spectra of the HSExp and the Gaussian pulse (a) in a region with severe (ROI 1: 47%, white circle in d) and moderate B_1 inhomogeneity (ROI 2: 69%, red circle in d). The MTR_{asym} curves in both ROI are shown in (e). Center slice asymmetry MTR_{asym} images at 1.3 ppm (b,f) and 0.25 ppm (c,g) of the Gaussian (b,c) and HSExp pulse (f,g) are shown. B_1 - (d) and B_0 -maps (h) show the inhomogeneity at UHF. In (g) the MTR_{asym} image shows artifacts in the anterior and posterior region, where the B_0 shift is ≥ 100 Hz. In this regime, the HSExp pulse is not stable enough. Oscillations appear in the asymmetry image of the Gaussian pulse (c). At 1.3 ppm (b,f), neither pulse generates visible oscillations and both MTR_{asym} images show a clear correlation with the B_1 -map.

Figure 10: Z-Spectrum (a) and MTR_{asym} curve (c) of a HSExp and Block pulse saturation scheme for different B₁ amplitudes in gray matter. Depicted Z-spectra originate from average of the whole GM segment generated using SPM [40]. With all amplitudes, the direct water saturation is smaller with the HSExp pulse and the Z-spectra are more narrow around the on-resonant frequency. Also, beyond 0.5 ppm, the HSExp pulse shows a higher asymmetry for all amplitudes. The MTR_{asym} images at 1.9 ppm with the HSExp (b) and rectangular pulse (d) with an amplitude of 2.5 μ T are shown. The error bars in (a) and (c) indicate the standard error in the GM ROI.